

Eliminating cobalt from lithium-ion batteries: which improvements can be enabled by the use of wet chemical routes?

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Background

Lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are important for the mobility sector's green energy transition by enabling the breakthrough of electric vehicles (EVs).

Challenge

The EV market's explosive growth will put considerable strain on the critical raw materials needed for LIB production. Especially the mining, refining, and processing of cobalt pose a number of challenges, ranging from social and environmental impacts to supply shortages.

Solution

LIB positive electrode materials containing little to none cobalt can be developed by the use of creative wet chemical synthesis routes.

H2020 COBRA

- Completely eliminate Co from the positive electrode
- High energy density (750 Wh/L) and cycle life (>2000 cycles) with fast charging (3 C)
- Competitive cost target (<90 €/kWh at pack level)

Synthesis of $\text{Li}_{1.1}\text{Ni}_{0.35}\text{Mn}_{0.55}\text{O}_2$ as Co-free, Li-rich layered oxide

Cycle stability of the material annealed at 700, 800, 900 °C.

Chemical solution synthesis of $\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ (LNMO) and Sn-doped lithium- and manganese rich NMC

Solution-gel synthesis of LNMO

SEM images and cycle stability of LNMO processed with natural and forced convection.

Co-precipitation of $\text{Li}_{1.2}\text{Ni}_{0.13}\text{Co}_{0.13}\text{Mn}_{0.54-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{O}_2$

XRD patterns of $\text{Li}_{1.2}\text{Ni}_{0.13}\text{Co}_{0.13}\text{Mn}_{0.54-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{O}_2$.

The mixed (Ni, Mn, Co) and (Ni, Co, Sn) elemental maps of $\text{Li}_{1.2}\text{Ni}_{0.13}\text{Co}_{0.13}\text{Mn}_{0.54-x}\text{Sn}_x\text{O}_2$.

TiO_x shells on $\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{1.5}\text{O}_4$ (LNMO) and $\text{LiNi}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$ (NMC-622)

Effect of annealing temperature on coated LNMO particles.

Rate capability of bare and coated NMC-622.

Conclusion

Whereas cobalt is ubiquitous in today's LIBs, current research efforts strive toward a reduction and elimination of cobalt in future LIBs. Our research contributes to the improvements required to make these novel materials competitive with the materials that are currently used in LIBs.

Affiliations

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